

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

TABLE S1. Sample information, including group assignments used in the diagnostic loci and fixed difference analyses

Collection code	Field number	Bioinformatics assembly name	County	State	Group assignment (npops=9)	Longitude ^a
–	spc16w0001	altwlm	Jeff Davis	TX	alterna	-103.93
–	spc17w0004	alt17w4f_TX	Jeff Davis	TX	alterna	-103.92
–	spc16w0002	altw2m	Jeff Davis	TX	alterna	-103.91
–	spc95w0002	alt95w2f_TX	Jeff Davis	TX	alterna	-103.91
–	spc17w0002	alt7w2f	Jeff Davis	TX	alterna	-103.93
KUH 288730	CAS 178	CAS178_KS	Johnson	KS	ks_5	-94.90
KUH 290660	CAS 265A	CAS265A_KS	Ellsworth	KS	ks_2	-97.99
KUH 290670	CAS 276	CAS276_KS	Douglas	KS	ks_4	-95.33
KUH 290671	CAS 277	CAS277_KS	Douglas	KS	ks_4	-95.33
KUH 290691	CAS 298	CAS298_KS	Douglas	KS	ks_4	-95.44
KUH 290692	CAS 299	CAS299_KS	Douglas	KS	ks_4	-95.44
FHSM 7627	–	F7627_KS	Woodson	KS	ks_4	-95.84
FHSM 7910	–	F7910_KS	Rush	KS	ks_1	-99.16
FHSM 7931	–	F7931_KS	Leavenworth	KS	ks_5	-94.99
FHSM 7991	–	F7991_KS	Leavenworth	KS	ks_4	-95.11
FHSM 8105	–	F8105_FL	Gulf	FL	elapsoides	-85.31
FHSM 8148	–	F8148_FL	Gulf	FL	elapsoides	-85.28
FHSM 8275	–	F8275_KS	Ness	KS	ks_1	-99.62
FHSM 8310	–	F8310_KS	Linn	KS	ks_5	-94.78
FHSM 8333	–	F8333_KS	Doniphan	KS	ks_4	-95.18
FHSM 8348	–	F8348_KS	Atchison	KS	ks_4	-95.17
FHSM 8351	–	F8351_KS	Doniphan	KS	ks_4	-95.09
FHSM 8447	–	F8447_KS	Ellsworth	KS	ks_2	-98.16
FHSM 8496	–	F8496_KS	Ness	KS	ks_1	-99.75
FHSM 8549	–	F8549_KS	Russell	KS	ks_2	-98.88
FHSM 8838	–	F8838_KS	Washington	KS	ks_3	-96.87
FHSM 8870	–	F8870_KS	Washington	KS	ks_3	-96.84
FHSM 9397	–	F9397_KS	Franklin	KS	ks_4	-95.08
FHSM 9636	–	F9636_KS	Rooks	KS	ks_1	-99.46
FHSM 9637	–	F9637_KS	Rooks	KS	ks_1	-99.46
FHSM 9650	–	F9650_KS	Rooks	KS	ks_1	-99.46
FHSM 9699	–	F9699_KS	Anderson	KS	ks_4	-95.15
FHSM 10175	–	F10175_FL	Gulf	FL	elapsoides	-85.30
FHSM 10526	–	F10526_KS	Russell	KS	ks_2	-98.68
FHSM 10600	–	F10600_KS	Greenwood	KS	ks_3	-96.04
FHSM 10601	–	F10601_KS	Greenwood	KS	ks_3	-96.04
FHSM 10616	–	F10616_KS	Bourbon	KS	ks_5	-94.82
FHSM 10797	–	F10797_KS	Douglas	KS	ks_4	-95.46
FHSM 10985	–	F10985_KS	Bourbon	KS	ks_5	-94.98
FHSM 10986	–	F10986_KS	Bourbon	KS	ks_5	-94.98
FHSM 10995	–	F10995_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.39
FHSM 11004	–	F11004_KS	Chase	KS	ks_3	-96.75
FHSM 11011	–	F11011_KS	Chase	KS	ks_3	-96.59
FHSM 11072	–	F11072_KS	Chase	KS	ks_3	-96.80
FHSM 11086	–	F11086_KS	Anderson	KS	ks_4	-95.24
FHSM 11271	–	F11271_KS	Ellis	KS	ks_1	-99.10
FHSM 11333	–	F11333_KS	Ellis	KS	ks_1	-99.21
FHSM 11338	–	F11338_KS	Ness	KS	ks_1	-99.70

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FHSM 11400	-	F11400_KS	Stanton	KS	reference_west	-102.01
FHSM 11512	-	F11512_KS	Anderson	KS	ks_4	-95.12
FHSM 11518	-	F11518_KS	Seward	KS	reference_west	-100.78
FHSM 12268	-	F12268_KS	Franklin	KS	ks_4	-95.10
FHSM 12299	-	F12299_KS	Russell	KS	ks_1	-99.02
FHSM 12492	-	F12492_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.41
FHSM 12501	-	F12501_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.38
FHSM 12655	-	F12655_KS	Finney	KS	reference_west	-100.98
FHSM 12786	-	F12786_KS	Leavenworth	KS	ks_4	-95.17
FHSM 12850	-	F12850_KS	Pottawatomie	KS	ks_3	-96.09
FHSM 12867	-	F12867_KS	Kiowa	KS	ks_1	-99.47
FHSM 12873	-	F12873_KS	Kiowa	KS	ks_1	-99.15
FHSM 12878	-	F12878_KS	Kiowa	KS	ks_1	-99.16
FHSM 12902	-	F12902_KS	Russell	KS	ks_2	-98.56
FHSM 12910	-	F12910_KS	Crawford	KS	ks_5	-94.83
FHSM 13122	-	F13122_KS	Wabaunsee	KS	ks_3	-96.04
FHSM 13514	-	F13514_KS	Pottawatomie	KS	ks_3	-96.09
FHSM 13668	-	F13668_KS	Ellis	KS	ks_1	-99.31
FHSM 13946	-	F13946_KS	Russell	KS	ks_2	-98.58
FHSM 14000	-	F14000_KS	Kearney	KS	reference_west	-101.13
FHSM 14488	-	F14488_KS	Franklin	KS	ks_4	-95.10
FHSM 14976	-	F14976_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.19
FHSM 14992	-	F14992_KS	Rush	KS	ks_1	-99.36
FHSM 15236	-	F15236_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.19
FHSM 15710	-	F15710_KS	Ellis	KS	ks_1	-99.24
FHSM 15711	-	F15711_KS	Lane	KS	reference_west	-100.26
FHSM 16397	-	F16397_KS	Bourbon	KS	ks_5	-94.98
FHSM 16447	-	F16447_KS	Rush	KS	ks_1	-99.36
FHSM 16634	-	F16634_KS	Grant	KS	reference_west	-101.34
FHSM 16635	-	F16635_KS	Grant	KS	reference_west	-101.34
KUH 332057	JRO 197	JRO197_KS	Johnson	KS	ks_5	-94.86
KUH 332058	JRO 198	JRO198_KS	Johnson	KS	ks_5	-94.86
TNHC 105687	TNHC-FS 08619	TF08619_KS	Leavenworth	KS	ks_5	-94.99
TNHC 105688	TNHC-FS 08620	TF08620_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.42
TNHC 105689	TNHC-FS 08621	TF08621_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.41
TNHC 105690	TNHC-FS 08622	TF08622_MO	Johnson	MO	reference_east	-94.10
KUH 348140	TNHC-FS 08625	TF08625_KS	Atchison	KS	ks_4	-95.16
KUH 348141	TNHC-FS 08626	TF08626_MO	Henry	MO	reference_east	-93.58
KUH 348142	TNHC-FS 08627	TF08627_MO	Henry	MO	reference_east	-93.53
KUH 348143	TNHC-FS 08628	TF08628_MO	Johnson	MO	reference_east	-93.62
KUH 348144	TNHC-FS 08629	TF08629_MO	Johnson	MO	reference_east	-93.60
KUH 348145	TNHC-FS 08630	TF08630_MO	Jackson	MO	reference_east	-94.22
KUH 348146	TNHC-FS 08631	TF08631_KS	Jefferson	KS	ks_4	-95.43
KUH 348147	TNHC-FS 08632	TF08632_MO	Platte	MO	reference_east	-94.74
KUH 348148	TNHC-FS 08633	TF08633_KS	Wyandotte	KS	ks_5	-94.91

Notes: CAS, Christopher A. Sheil; FHSM, Sternberg Museum of Natural History at Fort Hays State University; JRO, Jamie R. Oaks; KUH, University of Kansas Biodiversity Institute; spc, Troy Hibbitts personal collection; TCWC, Texas Cooperative Wildlife Collection (Texas A&M); TNHC-FS, UT Austin Biodiversity Collections field sample (collected by EAC).

^aLatitude values not provided because of concerns related to the commercial exploitation of these animals; we will provide latitude values to qualified investigators upon request for the purposes of re-analysis and reproducibility.

TABLE S2. Results of bioinformatics assembly pipeline for *Lampropeltis* dataset

<i>min_samples_locus</i> iPyrad parameter	Avg. read depth	Missing data ^a	Total sites	Total loci	Total SNPs	Total PIs	SNPs/locus	SNPs/site
112	11.01	15.49%	840,318	3,257	50,852	37,424	15.61	0.06
90	11.01	22.24%	2,541,106	9,783	161,929	119,404	16.55	0.06
45	11.01	37.72%	5,337,026	20,739	328,450	238,472	15.84	0.06

^aCalculated as the proportion of missing sites from total data matrix (not only SNPs).

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TABLE S3. Cross-validation analysis to compare spatial and non-spatial models within *conStruct* (Bradburd et al. 2018)

Replicate	Predictive accuracy ^a	
	Spatial	Non-spatial
1	0	-52.88
2	0	-71.14
3	0	-65.06
4	0	-68.75
5	0	-47.48
6	0	-61.94
7	0	-62.23
8	0	-69.25

^aPredictive accuracy is shown as the relative fit (difference in log-likelihood scores) of one model compared to the other; the best-fit model is set to zero.

TABLE S4. Models tested for the cline fitting analysis as implemented in the package *HZAR* (Derryberry et al. 2014)

Model	Scaling	Tails	Parameters	AIC
Model 1	Free	None	Cline center, cline width, pMin, pMax	9.453
Model 2	Free	Left tail only	Cline center, cline width, pMin, pMax, tauL, deltaL	13.806
Model 3	Free	Right tail only	Cline center, cline width, pMin, pMax, tauR, deltaR	14.085
Model 4	Free	Mirrored	Cline center, cline width, pMin, pMax, tauM, deltaM	14.043
Model 5	Free	Both independent	Cline center, cline width, pMin, pMax, tauL, deltaL, tauR, deltaR	18.770
Model 6	Fixed	None	Cline center, cline width	6.318

Notes: Frequency data were based on allele frequencies across all loci for each population. Allele frequencies were determined using 44 diagnostic loci observed between reference west and reference east populations and an 80% threshold for a locus to be considered diagnostic.

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TABLE S5. Pairwise fixed differences between seven longitudinally defined groups, including reference west and reference east groups, and also including samples from outgroups *L. alterna* and *L. elapsoides*

	reference west	ks_ 1	ks_ 2	ks_ 3	ks_ 4	ks_ 5	reference east	<i>L.</i> <i>alterna</i>	<i>L.</i> <i>elapsoides</i>
reference west	–								
ks_1	0	–							
ks_2	0	0	–						
ks_3	3	0	0	–					
ks_4	4	0	0	0	–				
ks_5	3	0	0	0	0	–			
reference east	9	5	5	4	0	0	–		
<i>L. alterna</i>	140	124	145	112	84	120	129	–	
<i>L. elapsoides</i>	83	65	76	60	47	57	62	187	–

Notes: Fixed differences were calculated using the *dartR* package in R (Gruber et al. 2018), and this analysis excludes the *L. alterna* hybrid individual.

TABLE S6. Pairwise fixed differences following iterative collapsing, calculated using the *dartR* package in R (Gruber et al. 2018).

	transect group ^a	<i>L. elapsoides</i>	<i>L. alterna</i>
transect group ^a	–	–	–
<i>L. elapsoides</i>	42	–	–
<i>L. alterna</i>	70	187	–

^atransect group includes 7 groups, collapsed: ks_1, ks_2, ks_3, ks_4, ks_5, reference west, and reference east.